

Student Reactions to Video Feedback Activities in Oral Communication and Presentation Courses

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Abstract: *In productive-skill courses, where students are often asked to engage in student-centered activities, instructors can find it difficult to provide individualized feedback when class sizes are large. To overcome this dilemma, some instructors have adopted methodologies that allow students to reflect on their own performances through self-assessment activities using video recordings. According to Hirata (2009), these activities have proven beneficial to students by raising “confidence and strength in their own language learning” (Hirata, 2009, p. 153). We have applied this methodology in oral communication and academic presentation courses while questioning its effectiveness from a student’s perspective. In this study, we conduct a preliminary investigation of a methodology that aims to promote noticing among groups of students with varying levels of English proficiency. The results indicate that respondents feel the combined use of instructor-scored rubrics along with the opportunity for self-assessment was ‘somewhat’ to ‘very helpful.’*

Keywords: self-assessment rubrics, video-recorded performances, pair-speaking tasks, academic presentation skills, self-reflection

Introduction

The benefits of videotaping for language learning purposes as well as the use of rubrics as a means for self-reflection and awareness raising are well represented in the literature. It has been established that video recordings of speaking tasks can help mediate second-language acquisition (SLA) by allowing learners to “see for themselves what has gone wrong in the operating conditions under which they went wrong” (Johnson, 1988, p. 93). Additionally, the use of videotaping as a tool for promoting motivation, communicative strategies (Murphey & Kenny, 1998; Murphey & Woo,

1998), noticing within oral performances, and enhanced practice (or multiple extended discourse opportunities – MEDOs) has been investigated, yielding positive results.

Since the mid-1980s, the importance of developing metacognitive skills in second language (L2) learning has been recognized (Wenden, 1987; Schraw & Dennison, 1994) as these skills can provide learners with an “opportunity to plan their learning, monitor their progress, or review their accomplishment” (O’Malley & Chamot, 1990, p. 8). Swain (2000), for example, has posited the notion that noticing can happen while learners are completing a task, and they can become aware of gaps that might impede their spoken production. Ellis (2003) has insisted that for L2 learners to notice the gaps in their production skills, metacognitive skills are necessary. Of importance to this study, Ellis calls for the creation of tasks to assist learners to “become aware of, reflect on, and evaluate their own learning styles and strategies they use to learn” (Ellis, 2003, p. 32).

Purpose of the Study

We have explored the potential of a methodology that incorporates the use of analytic self-assessment rubrics, video-recorded performances, and individual conferences for several years. Our rationale has been that if, according to Schmidt’s Noticing Hypothesis, “SLA is largely driven by what learners pay attention to and notice in target language input and what they understand the significance of noticed input to be” (Schmidt, 2001, pp. 3–4), a methodology which would encourage students to ‘pay attention’ to the important aspects of their performances should lead to increased performance. However, research was required to first establish whether such a methodology could enhance opportunities for noticing to occur, regardless of speaking task or proficiency level. Further, we wanted to understand the degrees to which students find such a methodology helpful, or unhelpful, before designing a study to measure its possible effects on actual performance.

Methodology

Setting and sample, participants, data analysis

The study was conducted with first- and second-year science and engineering students at a private university in Japan. First-year courses emphasize English for General Purposes (EGP) and second-year courses place an emphasis on English for Science and Technology (EST). Over five academic years (2015–2019), study participants were selected from a cross-section of English proficiency levels from compulsory oral communication and academic presentation classes that were offered in the spring and fall terms respectively: English Core I-a/II-a and English Core I-c/II-c. These courses were structured according to three levels of proficiency (Advanced, Intermediate, and Basic) with students “streamed” into level-appropriate classes based on a range of TOEIC Institutional Program (IP)[®] exam scores – (Advanced-level: 970–595 points, Intermediate-level: 590–340 points and Basic-level: 335 or fewer points). The English proficiency breakdown of the study participants is as follows: 15.1% Advanced-level students, 49.2% Intermediate-level students, and 35.6% Basic-level students.

Students in the first-semester oral communication classes are assessed through a five-minute, paired-speaking task which requires them to take part in an original, free-flowing conversation on topics previously studied in class. Specifically, students choose three to four topics to discuss from

a list of approximately ten topics. In the fall semester, students give individual academic presentations that vary in length according to level: Basic-level students do two-minute presentations (200 words in length), Intermediate-level students do four-minute presentations (400 words in length), and Advanced-level students do six-minute presentations (600 words in length). Presentation topics in the first year are related to students' personal interests, whereas second-year presentations are related to general science and engineering topics.

The rubric used for evaluating students in the first-semester oral communication course assesses five performance areas: syntax/structure, pronunciation, vocabulary, overall fluency and communicative strategies. This analytic rubric contains detailed performance descriptors on a performance proficiency scale of 1 to 10 for each skill. The second semester academic presentation course utilizes an analytic rubric that addresses two main aspects of presentations: content and delivery skills. The content category is made up of seven subsections: greeting, details, detail development, transition/signpost use, summary, overall preparedness, and visuals. The delivery skills are divided into nine subcategories: posture, hand position, facial expression, speaking volume, eye contact, no reading, speaking speed, appropriate English use, and pronunciation. This presentation scoring rubric also contains detailed performance descriptors and rates each skill on a scale of 1 to 5. For the Basic-level classes, simplified rubrics were used; however, identical rubrics were used in the Intermediate and Advanced-level classes.

While students prepared for their final speaking and presentation assessments at the end of the semester, the authors required students to watch their own videotaped midterm performances as a self-assessment activity. Students used the same assessment rubric as their teachers to complete this activity. Later in the term (usually two weeks before final assessments began), the authors met individually with students to compare actual midterm evaluation scores with the students' self-assessments. It was during these brief student-teacher conferences that we provided students with feedback regarding the strengths and weaknesses of their midterm performances, answered questions, and gave concrete suggestions for preparing for the upcoming final assessment. All scoring rubrics are written in Japanese (the students' L1) and in English.

On the last day of the semester, after all final assessments had been completed, students were asked to complete a 15-question survey (Appendix A) regarding their impressions of the course they had finished. The survey, consisting of 11 Likert scale questions and four open-ended questions, asked participants to reflect upon and rate their experiences with a teaching methodology that utilized a scoring rubric, videotaped speaking or presentation performances, and teacher-mediated feedback. Specifically, the survey attempts to isolate students' feelings regarding the usefulness of the teaching methodology and explores to what degree, if any, it was deemed to have had a positive effect on the participants' final, assessed performances.

A web-based survey system was used to collect survey responses at the end of the term (except for the 2015 data when data were collected at the end of the academic year). The survey questions were provided (and responses collected) in the participants' first language (L1): Japanese. Responses were recorded utilizing a 6-point Likert scale according to the following semantic anchors: 1=Strongly Disagree, 2=Disagree, 3=Somewhat Disagree, 4=Somewhat Agree, 5=Agree, 6=Strongly Agree. By the conclusion of the study, 1,623 surveys had been completed by 820 participants. Since the spring- and fall-term versions of the survey only differ slightly to reflect the differences in speaking tasks, data from both terms have been collapsed. The data collected in 2015 were collapsed as they are responses to the same questions about different semesters.

The authors gave similar instructions to the study participants before they completed the survey. Again, the participants were asked to reflect on the teaching approaches used in the course and to note the impact, if any, upon their final performances. The quantitative data were analyzed using methods appropriate to each research question, whereas the qualitative data (participants' comments) have been utilized to help uncover further insights to certain responses. Put more simply, this study's results contain findings that are illuminated by respondents' comments, thus, linking quantitatively significant findings to participant responses. To focus the investigation, we examined the data through four research questions, using the following statistical analyses:

- 1 **Do responses differ depending on class levels?** Pairwise comparisons using a Wilcoxon Rank Sum Test with continuity correction (Bonferroni correction) were used to investigate the responses. Initial results revealed that Q4, Q5, Q12, and Q14 may have different distributions depending on class levels. Histograms were created to compare the responses to these questions for each class level.
- 2 **Do responses differ depending on the years the data were collected?** Pairwise Comparisons, using a Wilcoxon Rank Sum Test with continuity correction (Bonferroni correction) were used to investigate the possible differences in responses depending on when the data were collected. Based on this data, histograms of the answers to Q1, Q5, Q8, Q11, and Q12 were created to further examine how the distributions might differ.
- 3 **Do responses differ depending on semesters?** A Pairwise Comparison, utilizing a Wilcoxon Rank Sum Test with continuity correction, was conducted on each question, and histograms were generated later to compare first- and second-semester data.
- 4 **Are there any significant correlations between (or among) answers to certain questions?** A correlation matrix was created first to discover if there are any notable relationships between questions. Later, to determine if a correlation between certain answers was statistically significant, Pearson product-moment correlation tests were conducted.

Figure 1. Correlation matrix of all Likert-scale questions.

Key Findings and Discussion

Research question #1: Do responses differ depending on class levels?

The data reveals that Q4 (Enough explanation about the rubric from the instructor was provided to the point that I clearly understood its contents) answers among Advanced-class members were more positively skewed compared to those of students in the Intermediate and Basic-level classes. The reason for this remains unclear as the instructors' explanations were given in English (the target language) in the Advanced-level classes, and in Japanese and in English in the Intermediate and Basic-level classes. As mentioned earlier, all rubrics have been produced in both English and the participants' L1.

Responses to Q5 (How many times did each student view their recorded performance?) produced different distributions per class level. Among Advanced-level students, the most frequent answer to Q5 (only by a small margin) was 1 (video viewed once), while the most frequent answer to this question in the Intermediate and Basic-level classes students was 2 (video viewed twice). The percentage of students who watched their video performances more than once was larger in the Intermediate-level and Basic-level classes. It was also noted that the percentage of students who did not watch their performances was largest in the Advanced-level classes.

Question 12 (It was enjoyable to have my performance recorded) revealed different distributions depending on class levels. The most frequent answer at all levels was 'somewhat agree,' meaning that most students felt that having their performance recorded was somewhat pleasant. However, a higher percentage of students thought it was pleasant to have their performances recorded in the Basic-level classes, and a lower percentage of students in the Intermediate and Advanced-level classes agreed that being video recorded was enjoyable.

Basic-level classes have a different distribution of answers to Q14 (Discussing my own evaluation with the instructor helped me to improve my communication/presentation skills). Specifically, the answers for Q14 were more negatively skewed in Basic-level classes compared to the Advanced and Intermediate-level classes.

Upon closer examination, the histograms reveal that Basic-level students were slightly more negative toward this aspect of the methodology. The number of students who 'strongly disagree,' 'disagree,' and 'somewhat disagree' combined was 46/507(9.1%) among Basic-level students, 34/861(4.0%) among Intermediate-level students, and 14/246(5.3%) among Advanced-level students. Accordingly, the proportion of students who disagreed with the idea of having a post-assessment conference with the instructor to help them improve their performance was larger among Basic-level students when compared to Intermediate-level and Advanced-level students.

The responses to Q15 (What makes you think that?) were examined to consider the possible reasons why more Basic-level students did not take the opportunity to discuss their speaking evaluation with their teacher. Basic-level students who 'disagreed' with Q14 wrote comments such as: "We did not have time to discuss." This was the most frequent answer. "We didn't have a discussion" was the second most frequent answer. Other common responses included: "It was too embarrassing to watch" and "Because the rubric is easy to understand, viewing the video by myself is sufficient to assess my performance."

Overall, among the Basic-level students who did not think the post-assessment, teacher-student conference was useful either did not have an opportunity for an actual conference or did not believe that the conference was necessary, and hence, thought the teacher-student conference did

not help them improve their performance. Amongst the Intermediate-level students, representative comments to Q15 included: "I did not have enough time to talk with the instructor" (The most frequent answer). "Rather than talking about the assessment, I just listened to the instructor talk about my score"; "I didn't watch my video"; "It was unnecessary to watch my video"; "There are so many students, and the teacher doesn't need to talk to each one of us."

Among the Intermediate-level students, the reasons for disagreeing with Q14 (By watching and scoring my performance, then later discussing my performance with my teacher, my overall communication skills have improved) were linked to a belief that the conferences were either not useful, or because they did not understand the discrepancies between their instructor's assessments and their own. Among the Advanced-level students who disagreed with the statement in Q14, the most common explanations were: "I didn't want to watch my performance"; "I didn't want to face it"; "It was not objective"; "Even though I understood what needs to be improved, without practice my performance will not be perfect"; "We did not compare our assessments with each other."

The comments above might suggest that some students felt that the time allocated to discuss their assessment was insufficient (or there was no time at all) and, thus, responded negatively. The Advanced-level students, who disagreed with the statement in Q14, frequently described that the reasons for their responses were due to in-class time constraints – "Practice is needed no matter what." Such responses underscore the importance of allocating enough time for post-assessment, student-teacher conferences and practice. Moreover, other comments also suggest that instructors must carefully explain the differences between the student/teacher evaluations and demonstrate how students might apply their performance challenges (as well as strengths) to real-world communication.

Research question #2: Do responses differ depending on the years the data were collected?

Overall, statistically significant differences in the data were not discovered; however, study participants in 2015 did answer more negatively to Q1 (I feel that the assessment rubric used in class has helped me to improve my overall communication/presentation skills) when compared with the responses gathered in 2017, 2018, and 2019. To investigate the possible reasons why those participants disagreed with the statement, responses to Q2 (What makes you think that?) were considered.

Basic-level students in 2015 mentioned the following: "Everyone was unmotivated" and "I did not practice enough." The 2017 and 2018 Basic-level class participants made comments such as "I was sleepy because of the time of class" and "I did not practice pronunciation." The Basic-level students tended to give irrelevant reasons for disagreeing with the statement in Q1.

The Intermediate-level student responses to Q2 (What makes you think that?) were also varied and inconclusive: "I did not read well"; "Due to my lack of vocabulary, I cannot write good sentences"; "I don't know exactly what needs to be improved"; "I didn't understand some parts"; "I couldn't make use of the rubric for the next time." Again, among the Intermediate and Basic-level students, comments are mostly irrelevant to the use of the rubric, offering, for instance, not having enough time to prepare for their performances was the reason for disagreeing with Q1.

Advanced-level students in 2015 wrote more concrete and valid reasons for disagreeing with the statement in Q1 (I feel that the assessment rubric used in class has helped me to improve my overall communication/presentation skills). Some students, for example, claimed that their

performances would not improve in a short amount of time, or that prepared presentation scripts and daily conversations are different types of speaking tasks.

Based upon the comments from all class levels across all years, the authors believe it is critical that students evaluate their own performances by utilizing the same rubric (used for evaluating students) while they are viewing the video-taped performances, as they are clearly instructed to do. Moreover, based on participants' comments, instructors must allocate enough time for the self-evaluation conferences to explain to students how performance content and/or observed communication skills might be applied to daily, unpracticed conversations. Perhaps by making these types of explicit connections, more students will understand the value of the assessment rubric.

Research question #3: Do responses differ depending on semesters?

The responses to Questions 1, 3, 4, 5, 6, 8, 10 and 13 were all positively skewed in the second semester. However, no significant differences between the first and second semester responses to Q11 (Having my performance recorded motivated me to prepare for my presentation), Q12 (It was enjoyable to have my presentation recorded), or Q14 (Discussing about my own evaluation with the instructor helped me to improve my presentation) were observed; furthermore, respondents' comments failed to produce any clear rationale for this. The authors can only infer that students answered more positively to Questions 1, 3, 4, 5, 6, 8, 10 and 13 in the second semester because of their familiarity with the teaching methodology and its potential impact on their learning outcomes.

Research question #4: Are there any significant correlations between (or among) answers to certain questions?

The data from the correlation matrix revealed diverse results. Firstly, answers to Q5 (The number of times I viewed my recorded performance) are not strongly correlated with the other questions, and the reason for this remains unclear. It would seem counterintuitive that Q5 did not produce a strong correlation with Q6 (Viewing my own recorded presentation and evaluating it with the rubric helped to improve my communication/presentation skills), for example. Similarly, data analysis reveals that Q11 (Having my performance recorded motivated me to prepare for my presentation) and Q12 (It was enjoyable to have my presentation recorded) have a weaker correlation than with the other survey questions. This might suggest that either, 1.) the number of times students viewed their performances does not correlate with how impactful they believe the rubric assessment is in terms of improving their oral communication/presentation skills, or 2.) even if students did not enjoy having their performances recorded, nor believe that it helped to encourage them to put in more effort in their final performances, they still found the assessment rubrics helpful to improve their overall oral communication/presentation skills. Secondly, analysis shows that among the students who answered positively ('Strongly Agree,' 'Agree,' and 'Somewhat Agree') toward Q1 (The rubric helped me to improve my communication ability), 99.6% of them answered positively to Q3 (The rubric helped me to understand my strength and weakness of my presentation). It should be noted if we combine only "Strongly Agree" and "Agree" and define those two responses as positive answers, 89% of students who answered positively to Q1 also answered positively to Q3.

Andrade (2000) explains that "all rubrics have two features in common: 1.) a list of criteria, or 'what counts' in a project or assignment; and 2.) gradations of quality, with descriptions of strong, middling, and problematic student work" (p. 13). Thus, rubrics help to provide helpful feedback while pointing out specific features which are important in determining quality. The last correlation

between the survey questions reveals how many participants connected the two notions of evaluative criteria and performance quality: Q1 (I feel that the assessment rubric used in class has helped me to improve my overall communication/presentation skills) and Q4 (The assessment rubric used in class was explained to me to the point which I clearly understood its contents) resulted in a strong correlation. This finding, while seemingly self-evident, underscores the importance of instructors taking the necessary time to thoroughly explain the assessment rubrics to students.

Conclusions

In this study, we have discovered that the methodology under investigation was able to provide opportunities for noticing to occur when students were preparing to give final performances in oral communication and academic presentation classes, regardless of proficiency level. One student wrote, "By watching the video of myself, I was able to check the actions I had done unconsciously and consciously pay attention to them next time." Another student stated, "I had given myself low evaluation scores and had no idea what my strengths were, but I was able to gain confidence by comparing my score with the teacher's score." In fact, 92.2% of the study participants found the teaching methodology that combined the use of scoring rubrics with the opportunity for self-assessment of speaking tasks to be 'somewhat' to 'very helpful.' While other reactions to the methodology were mixed and inconclusive, this study does suggest that instructors should explain their teaching approaches carefully to students and attempt, when possible, to connect these approaches to possible benefits outside of classroom learning. Lastly, the study further suggests that teacher-student conferences should occur only after instructors are confident that students have watched their videotaped performances and can present their rubric-based, self-assessment scores at the teacher-student conference.

Pedagogical Implications

Arguments for the use of assessment rubrics coupled with face-to-face feedback in English as a Foreign Language (EFL) learning contexts can be found in the literature. In the case of L2 writing instruction, for example, Mahmoudi & Buğra (2020) have argued that not only do rubrics serve as a means of evaluation but also as an important tool for learning. Additionally, the authors agree with the seven benefits of instructional rubrics as outlined by Andrade (2000): "1.) They are easy to be used and explained, 2.) They make teachers' expectations very obvious, 3.) They provide students with more informative feedback about their strengths and weaknesses, 4.) They support learning, 5.) They support skills development, 6.) They support the development of understanding, and 7.) They support good thinking." Based on this study, we have found that the "benefits" of instructional rubrics ultimately promote noticing and the development of metacognitive skills in meaningful ways.

This study offers some support for a methodology which utilizes analytic rubrics for student self-assessment and final assessment purposes. Coupled with the use of videotaping to capture speaking performances, which in turn can be used to facilitate reflection and self-evaluation activities, this methodology is clearly worth the effort on the part of instructors. Furthermore, based on the findings that include comments by study participants, more time should have been devoted to the student-teacher conferences. To ensure the highest quality of mediated feedback, instructors

must provide enough time to compare and discuss any assessment discrepancies while drawing attention to specific rubric descriptors that are manifested in student performances.

Limitations of the Current Study

While this study has provided some insights into the attitudes and behaviors of students in reaction to one teaching methodology, there are several limitations that must be addressed. First, the sample population was drawn from one institution and among undergraduate science and engineering majors only. Moreover, the study was restricted to one geographic region, thus reflecting the attitudes and behaviors of a single culture. This fact will limit the generalizability of the findings to a larger and more diverse population. Also problematic is the omission of the gender and age data of the participants. Finally, since students may have provided socially desirable responses, response biases might be present in the findings. Despite these limitations, the authors hope this study will provide some groundwork for future research.

Acknowledgements

The authors would like to acknowledge their deepest appreciation to Hiroko Baker for her assistance with the statistical analyses. This study benefitted greatly through her keen technical skills and thoughtful insights. Additionally, the authors must thank Nanako Jyojima and Tetsuo Aoyama at the Aoyama Gakuin University Institute of Information and Media for providing critical resources and support for this research project. Finally, we would like to thank the participants who generously volunteered their time and opinions to make this study a success.

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Appendix A

Note: Questions 2, 7, 9, 15, 17, 22, 24, and 30 are open-ended questions that ask the same qualitative question regarding the preceding question: “What makes you think that?”

- Q1:** I feel that the assessment rubric used in the English Core I-a (or II-a) class has helped me to improve my overall oral communication skills.
- Q3:** I feel that the assessment rubric used in the English Core I-a (or II-a) class has helped me to understand my strengths and weaknesses with spoken English communication.
- Q4:** The assessment rubric used in the English Core I-a (or II-a) class was explained to me to the point which I clearly understood its contents.
- Q5:** I watched my video recorded performance that was taken in the English Core I-a (or II-a) class.
- Q6:** I feel that by scoring my video recorded performance with the assessment rubric has helped me to improve my overall communication skills.
- Q8:** I feel that by comparing my assessment score with the teacher’s score has helped me to improve my overall communication skills.
- Q10:** Comparing my assessment scores with the teacher’s scores has helped me to prepare for my next graded performance.
- Q11:** I feel that because my performance was video recorded, I put more effort in preparing for my assignment.
- Q12:** I enjoyed being video recorded in class.
- Q13:** I feel that the combined use of the scoring rubric along with the opportunity to watch my recorded performance has helped me to improve my overall communication skills.
- Q14:** I feel that by watching and scoring my performance, then later discussing my performance with my teacher, my overall communication skills have improved. (I think that it is useful for students to meet their teachers to discuss their scores.)
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- Q16:** I feel that the assessment rubric used in the English Core I-c (or II-c) class has helped me to improve my overall presentation skills.
- Q18:** After assessing myself using the rubric, I was able to understand my strong and weak presentation skill areas more concretely.
- Q19:** The assessment rubric used in the English Core I-c (or II-c) class was explained to me to the point which I clearly understood its contents.

- Q20:** I watched my video recorded performance taken in the English Core I-c (or II-c) class.
- Q21:** I feel that by scoring my (video recorded) presentation with the assessment rubric has helped me to improve my overall presentation skills.
- Q23:** I feel that by comparing my assessment scores with the teacher's scores has helped me to improve my next presentation.
- Q25:** I feel that by comparing my assessment scores with the teacher's scores has helped me to better prepare for my next presentation.
- Q26:** I feel that because my presentation was video recorded, I put more effort in preparing for my assignment.
- Q27:** I enjoyed having my presentation video recorded in class.
- Q28:** I feel that scoring my (video recorded) presentation with the assessment rubric has helped me to improve my overall presentation skills.
- Q29:** I feel that by watching and scoring my presentation, then later discussing my presentation with my teacher, my overall presentation skills have improved. (I think that it is useful for students to meet their teachers to discuss their scores.)